

Beyond the silence: Legal pathways to protect children born of conflict-related sexual violence in Ukraine

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I. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Children born conflict-related sexual violence (CBoCRSV) represent one of the most vulnerable and least visible groups affected by the ongoing conflict in Ukraine. While Ukraine has taken meaningful steps to strengthen legal frameworks addressing conflict-related sexual violence (CRSV) – including recognition of CRSV as a war crime and crime against humanity, improvements in birth registration pathways, and the introduction of interim reparations mechanisms – significant gaps remain in implementation, service access, legal clarity, and long-term protection.

This report brings together findings from a six-month research and policy process, combining legal and policy analysis using a structured assessment toolkit with insights from multi-stakeholder workshops involving government representatives, civil society, service providers, legal experts, people with lived experience and survivor advocates.

a. Key Findings

The assessment identified challenges across five core domains:

- **Stigma and public attitudes:** Fear of exposure and judgement prevents many families from seeking services, particularly in small communities.
- **Fragmented legal status:** CBoCRSV are not yet recognised as a distinct legal category, resulting in inconsistent access to rights and services.
- **Uneven service implementation:** While legal pathways exist, regional variation, unclear procedures, and limited trauma-informed capacity hinder equitable access.
- **Identity and documentation challenges:** Birth registration and adoption processes remain complex, especially where cases involve secrecy, displacement, or lack of documentation.
- **Limited integration in national strategies:** While CRSV survivors are increasingly recognised, children remain largely absent from existing policy frameworks and reparations systems.

The assessment has repeatedly emphasised that **CBoCRSV are currently “administered through categories rather than recognised as a protected identity,”** creating a risk that they remain invisible within otherwise functioning systems.

b. Priority Recommendations

The report proposes six overarching recommendations to establish a rights-based framework for CBoCRSV:

1. **Establish a harmonised legal definition of CBoCRSV**, reflected consistently across laws on justice, identity, social protection, adoption, and reparations.
2. **Create confidential, trauma-informed pathways for access to services**, including birth registration, healthcare, psychosocial support, and assistance with legal documentation.

3. **Develop a coordinated national referral and case management system** that reduces duplication, prevents retraumatisation, and ensures predictable support.
4. **Launch a survivor-informed national stigma reduction and public information strategy**, grounded in research and rolled out in phases.
5. **Strengthen workforce capacity across sectors**, including judiciary, civil registry, health, education, and social services, using standardised training and ongoing supervision.
6. **Establish ethical, confidential monitoring and evaluation mechanisms** to track access, equity, and outcomes without labelling or exposing children.

These recommendations align with international standards, emerging Ukrainian legal reforms, and comparative learning from other transitional justice contexts.

c. Roadmap for Implementation

A phased roadmap is proposed to operationalise these reforms:

Phase	Timeframe	Core Objectives
Phase 1 – Foundation	0–12 months	Clarify legal definitions; establish confidential service pathways; pilot training and targeted communication.
Phase 2 – System Integration	12–24 months	Implement coordinated referral system; expand adoption and birth registration safeguards; embed monitoring processes.
Phase 3 – Sustainability & Scale	24–36+ months	Strengthen cross-sector standards; mainstream identity and reparations access; embed public messaging in national systems.

Throughout all phases, implementation must be guided by:

- **The best interests of the child**
- **Do-no-harm and confidentiality principles**
- **Survivor-centred participation**
- **Equity and consistency across regions**

d. Conclusion

Ukraine has already laid essential foundations for protecting survivors of conflict-related sexual violence. The next step is to extend this protection to children born of these violations – not as dependents, but as rights-holders. By adopting a coordinated, ethical, and future-focused approach, Ukraine has the opportunity to become a global leader in recognising and supporting children born of wartime rape while the conflict is ongoing.

“We cannot change what happened – but we can shape what comes next.”

II. INTRODUCTION

a. Background and context

The conflict in Ukraine began in 2014 with the illegal annexation of Crimea and the onset of hostilities in the Donetsk and Luhansk regions. Since then, the nature and scale of violations—including sexual violence—have evolved alongside changing territorial control, patterns of occupation, displacement, and military operations.

The full-scale invasion in February 2022 transformed the conflict's scope and intensity. Large-scale displacement, temporary occupation, filtration procedures, and widespread detention conditions created new environments in which conflict-related sexual violence (CRSV) became increasingly documented. CRSV has been reported across:

- temporarily occupied territories,
- areas under active hostilities,
- detention and filtration settings,
- during forced displacement or movement across borders.

The conflict has also weakened institutional capacity in affected regions, disrupted civil registration systems, and strained the health, social protection, and justice sectors. As a result, access to services—particularly confidential and trauma-informed services—varies significantly across regions.

International bodies, including the United Nations, the Office of the Prosecutor General of Ukraine, and civil society organisations, recognise CRSV in Ukraine as a conflict-related pattern. The response now includes dedicated investigative structures, survivor support and documentation mechanisms, and emerging reparations frameworks.

Despite significant progress, the system remains in active development and operates under wartime conditions. The ongoing nature of the conflict means many survivors are still deciding whether to disclose their experiences, and many children born of CRSV are still in infancy or early childhood.

Scope and Relevance of CBoCRSV as a Legal and Policy Concern

Children born of conflict-related sexual violence (CBoCRSV) represent a distinct group with specific legal, psychological, and social protection needs. Their experiences exist at the intersection of human rights, child protection, transitional justice, and public health.

These children may face multiple vulnerabilities, including:

- Risk of legal identity barriers, especially where documentation is incomplete or created during occupation;
- Exposure to stigma and social exclusion linked to circumstances of conception;
- Complex family dynamics, including ambivalence or trauma-related responses from parents or extended family;
- Unequal access to reparations and long-term rights if not explicitly recognised in legislation and policy frameworks.

While the mother-survivor is recognised under current CRSV legislation and reparation measures, the legal position of the child born of such violence remains less clearly defined. Without explicit legal recognition, eligible children may be excluded from:

- compensation schemes,
- long-term healthcare support,
- identity-rights mechanisms,
- psychosocial assistance,
- access to justice as secondary victims of war crimes.

Furthermore, because some children affected are newborns or have not yet reached developmental stages where identity and belonging are conscious, the policy response must include forward-planning and anticipatory protection, not only immediate crisis intervention.

The relevance of CBoCRSV extends beyond the individual to broader societal and post-conflict recovery goals. A rights-based, survivor-informed response contributes to:

- preventing intergenerational trauma,
- ensuring equality before the law,
- strengthening institutional trust,
- countering harmful narratives rooted in gender, ethnicity, or nationality,
- shaping social cohesion in post-war reconstruction.

“The child carries the war into the future – not because of who they are, but because of what society believes about them.”

*~ Service provider,
Psychosocial support field*

For Ukraine—where national identity, dignity, and justice are central to the resistance and recovery narrative—ensuring that children born of wartime rape are recognised and protected is not only a legal obligation, but also a statement of values.

b. Methodology

This report represents the final output of a six-month research and policy project led by GRACE International, funded through UK Research and Innovation via the University of Birmingham (UK). The project examined the legal, policy, and implementation landscape affecting CBoCRSV in Ukraine.

The analysis was conducted using a structured assessment toolkit designed to identify strengths, weaknesses, and gaps within the legal and policy framework relevant to CBoCRSV. The Toolkit was first reviewed and validated with experts and practitioners at a stakeholder workshop in the UK. A second workshop held in Ukraine provided additional validation, refinement, and expansion of the assessment based on national context, practitioner feedback, and lived experience insights.

This report brings together the findings from:

- The Toolkit-based legal and policy assessment
- Workshop discussions and survivor-informed insights

- Perspectives from government, civil society organisations, frontline practitioners, and international experts
- Comparative learning drawn from international practice where relevant

Workshop voices are included carefully and selectively. Quotations are used only where they illuminate systemic experience and do not reveal personal identities. All contributions are anonymised and presented in a way that centres dignity and protection from harm.

III. VOICES AND LIVED EXPERIENCE

This section reflects the human realities behind the policy landscape. While laws and procedures define structures, lived experiences illuminate gaps, consequences, and the emotional and social context in which decisions are made.

Quotations are intentionally concise and anonymised by role or category. They are not case studies; they are signals of systemic experience.

a. The Impact of War and Sexual Violence

Survivors of conflict-related sexual violence describe profound disruption—not only physical harm but emotional fragmentation, loss of identity, and complex feelings toward pregnancy and motherhood. Experiences varied based on setting, access to support, and levels of stigma within families and communities.

“The war came into my life suddenly. I did not understand what was happening... and afterwards, I didn’t know where to go for help.”
~ Survivor, workshop discussion

Some described pregnancies as unimaginably difficult decisions,

especially when occurring in environments lacking confidentiality or support.

These emotional realities demonstrate the need for specialised trauma-informed care, respect for autonomy, and structured support systems.

I hated myself, I hated the situation, and I did not know if I could love the child.”
~Survivor and mother of CBoCRSV

b. Fear of Disclosure and Community Stigma

Across discussions, stigma emerged as one of the most persistent barriers. Small-town environments amplify fear, as local authorities, service providers, and neighbours are often socially connected.

This fear delays or prevents access to:

- Birth registration
- Health care
- Mental health services
- Social protection
- Justice or reparations

Women have reported making decisions—not based on what is best for them or their child—but based on what will avoid attention.

c. Identity, Belonging, and Emotional Development

Several contributors emphasised that children born of CRSV may face different emotional risks depending on how the pregnancy and birth are framed within the family and community.

“In a small village, everyone knows everything. You think: if I ask for help, the whole village will know before I even leave the building.”

~ Psychologist working with survivors

“Some children grow up loved and protected. Others grow up in silence and tension – even if nobody ever speaks of it.”

~ Child psychologist

These factors indicate the need for long-term psychosocial programmes addressing:

- Mother–child bonding
- Identity formation
- Intergenerational trauma
- Safe disclosure and truth-telling frameworks

d. Adoption, Confidentiality, and Long-Term Rights

Cases were raised where children born of CRSV were adopted without full informed consent or without safeguarding long-term rights to identity and reparations.

Stakeholders expressed concern that **confidentiality rules**, if not carefully balanced, could unintentionally **erase future entitlements** or prevent trauma-informed identity support.

“The child disappeared into the system. Maybe she will find out one day – but maybe she never will.”

~ NGO legal advocate

e. Hope, Resilience, and Advocacy

“I cannot change what happened to me. But I can help change what happens next.”

– Survivor advocate

Despite trauma, many participants demonstrated resilience and determination to change systems for others.

This collective agency reflects readiness for policy reform and provides a strong foundation for a coordinated national response.

IV. LEGAL AND POLICY LANDSCAPE IN UKRAINE

Ukraine has made significant progress in aligning its legal and policy frameworks with international standards related to conflict-related sexual violence (CRSV). While the framework is strengthening, implementation remains uneven across sectors, and specific protections for CBoCRSV are not yet fully harmonised. The legal landscape relevant to these children spans criminal law, civil registration and identity law, social protection systems, reparations and transitional justice mechanisms, and national policy strategies. Legal clarity is

essential not only for birth registration and identity rights, but also for access to reparations, various forms of support, and justice.

This section presents an expanded examination of the national legal and policy landscape relevant to CBoCRSV, including areas of alignment, gaps, and implications for practice.

a. Constitutional and Foundational Legal Guarantees

Ukraine's Constitution provides several core protections relevant to CBoCRSV, including:

- The right to dignity and protection from degrading treatment
- Equal access to public services and rights regardless of birth status
- The rights of the child to protection and development
- State obligation to uphold international treaties

These guarantees form the legal foundation for rights-based policy and service response.

However, while these provisions apply in principle, they do not explicitly reference children born of sexual violence, which leaves interpretation to administrative discretion and judicial practice.

b. International Treaty Commitments

Ukraine is party to key international human rights and humanitarian instruments relevant to CRSV and children's rights, including:

- Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC)
- Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW)
- Geneva Conventions and Additional Protocols
- Rome Statute (withdrawal of declaration reservations underway)
- Council of Europe Istanbul Convention (ratified 2022)

These instruments require:

- Protection from violence
- Access to care and support
- Non-discrimination on grounds of birth or status
- Effective justice and reparations

The Istanbul Convention, in particular, strengthens obligations to provide coordinated support systems for survivors and affected children. Full implementation is ongoing.

c. Criminal Law and Justice Framework

Ukraine's criminal legal framework provides multiple pathways to prosecute conflict-related sexual violence (CRSV), reflecting both ordinary criminal law and international criminal law standards. However, gaps remain in implementation, case classification, and alignment with

survivor and child-sensitive justice processes—particularly relevant for children born of CRSV (CBoCRSV).

Legal Definitions and Applicable Criminal Offences

CRSV can be prosecuted under three parallel legal categories in Ukraine:

- As ordinary sexual crimes under Articles 152–156-1 of the Criminal Code (rape, sexual assault, grooming, sexual exploitation)
- As a war crime under Article 438, recognising sexual violence as a method or consequence of armed conflict
- As a crime against humanity under the newly introduced Article 442-1, following alignment with the Rome Statute

The Criminal Code adopts a consent-based definition of rape, consistent with the Istanbul Convention, where absence of voluntary consent—not proof of physical resistance—is decisive. This reflects international jurisprudence that recognises coercive conflict environments inherently negate consent.

Child-Sensitive Criminal Procedure

Ukraine’s Criminal Procedure Code includes extensive protections for child victims and witnesses, including:

- Privacy and confidentiality requirements (Art. 27)
- Specialised interview procedures requiring psychologists, educators, or medical staff (Arts. 226–227)
- Video-recorded testimony options to prevent repeated questioning (Art. 232)
- Protective courtroom measures, including removing minors during distressing testimony (Art. 495)

These safeguards align with global best practices and help reduce secondary trauma—critical in CRSV cases involving children conceived through violence.

Persistent Gaps in Conflict Qualification

Despite legal provisions, many CRSV cases continue to be charged under “ordinary” sexual offence articles rather than as war crimes or crimes against humanity.

This misclassification results in:

- Loss of victim-of-war status
- Reduced eligibility for reparations under Law 4067-IX
- Lower sentencing thresholds
- Fragmented or delayed access to specialized services

“Without the conflict context in the charge, the survivor becomes ‘just another criminal case’, not a victim of war.”

~ Workshop participant

Intersection With Reparations and Civil Claims

Survivors may pursue civil compensation within criminal proceedings or through separate civil lawsuits. Practitioners recommend integrated proceedings to avoid duplication and reduce survivor burden.

However, barriers remain, including:

- Perpetrators lacking assets to satisfy compensation orders
- Statutes of limitation uncertainty for ordinary criminal charges vs. war crimes, which have no limitation period under international law
- Tensions between confidentiality and evidence collection, especially as the number of cases grows and may inform international prosecutions (e.g., ICC)

Relevance for CBoCRSV

Although children born of CRSV are not direct complainants in sexual violence prosecutions, criminal case classification has downstream effects, including:

<i>Legal Outcome</i>	<i>Impact on CBoCRSV</i>
Case classified as war crime / crime against humanity	Enables recognition as secondary victim; facilitates reparations and long-term protective status
Case classified as ordinary crime	May block child's access to recognition, reparations, or specialised protections
Criminal proceedings absent/delayed	Survivor may still access administrative reparations, but identity and documentation for the child may remain contested

Under Law 4067-IX, CBoCRSV are recognised as survivors entitled to interim reparations without requiring a conviction. However, harmonisation gaps remain with other legislative instruments and registries.

Key Implementation Barriers

- Inconsistent knowledge and training among prosecutors and judges
- Limited awareness of how coercive wartime environments negate consent
- Risk of retraumatisation during evidence-gathering
- Tension between confidentiality and future truth-seeking (e.g., identity rights for children)

d. Civil and Family Law: Birth Registration and Identity

Birth registration is essential for CBoCRSV to access health care, education, social support, and legal protections. Under Ukrainian law, every child has the right to be registered immediately after birth and to receive a birth certificate regardless of the circumstances of conception or parental identity. The legal framework recognises the child—not parental history—as the basis for citizenship and identity.

In recent years, Ukraine has strengthened civil registration mechanisms to address conflict-related displacement and the war's administrative disruptions. These reforms include

simplified judicial and administrative pathways for registering children born in temporarily occupied territories, as well as procedures recognising documents issued under duress or outside standard state structures. Despite these measures, the system remains uneven in practice.

The assessment has highlighted several challenges in implementation:

- **Fear and stigma:** Families may hesitate to access registration procedures due to fear that the circumstances of conception could become publicly known or documented in official systems.
- **Documentation gaps:** Many survivors lack access to standard documents (e.g., medical birth records, paternal information, or identification documents lost during displacement), which may trigger additional administrative steps or judicial confirmation.
- **Variable administrative practice:** Some civil registry officials remain uncertain about how to process cases where no paternal information is available, despite legal mechanisms permitting birth certificates to be issued without naming a father.
- **Court confirmation delays:** Birth certificates issued in temporarily occupied territories may require judicial review or confirmation, leading to uncertainty and delayed access to services.

These administrative inconsistencies result in differential outcomes depending on geographic location, the discretion of officials, and a survivor's ability or willingness to engage with institutions.

Adoption and Identity Rights

Adoption law introduces an additional layer of complexity for CBoCRSV. Ukraine's legal framework prioritises the child's best interests and protects the confidentiality of adoption records. Confidentiality may shield children from stigma and unwanted disclosure; however, it may also inadvertently prevent them from accessing essential rights later in life, including:

- Eligibility for reparations as secondary victims of conflict-related sexual violence
- Information supporting psychological and identity development
- Family medical and genetic history for health decision-making
- Legal recognition in future accountability or transitional justice mechanisms

The assessment has identified this as a **legal and ethical dilemma**: safeguards designed to protect privacy can unintentionally obscure identity and limit access to long-term rights. The absence of explicit legal guidance on identity disclosure in cases of CRSV-related adoption leaves decisions to case-by-case discretion, risking inconsistency and inequity.

The Core Policy Tension: Confidentiality vs. Recognition

Balancing anonymity and identity protection remains an unresolved and sensitive legal challenge. The Toolkit emphasises that:

- Over-protection through secrecy may erase future rights.
- Under-protection may expose survivors and children to stigma or harm.

Best practice frameworks suggest a **graduated rights model**, where identity information is securely stored and becomes accessible to the child based on age, developmental readiness, and legal framework—not public access or administrative discretion.

Key Implications

1. **Access to rights depends on documentation.** Without registration, children cannot access essential services or protection.
2. **Inconsistent implementation undermines equity.** Clear national protocols and training are needed to ensure uniform application.
3. **Identity is a long-term need, not a single administrative act.** Protection must extend beyond infancy into adolescence and adulthood.

e. Social Protection and Welfare Systems

CBoCRSV do not yet have a harmonised or explicitly recognised legal status within Ukraine’s national social protection architecture. Instead, they are administratively absorbed into broader vulnerability categories such as:

- *Orphan or “semi-orphan”*
- *Internally displaced child*
- *Child from a socially vulnerable family*
- *Child of a survivor of violence*

While these categories provide a baseline safety net, they do not reflect the specific rights, risks, or long-term social and psychological needs associated with being born of wartime rape. The Toolkit emphasises that the absence of a formal, identity-linked status not only affects immediate access to services, but also influences reparations, monitoring, and long-term policy planning.

Fragmentation and Inconsistent Eligibility

Because CBoCRSV are not explicitly recognised in legislation or administrative guidance, frontline decision-making relies heavily on interpretation and regional discretion. As a result:

- Some children may receive multiple overlapping supports, often because their caseworker recognises heightened vulnerability.
- Others may receive no benefits, particularly when parents avoid disclosure due to stigma, fear of exposure, or uncertainty about the consequences.
- Eligibility for financial or social benefits varies depending on which vulnerability category a child is placed into, rather than on the circumstances of conception.

Workshop participants described this as a disconnect between legal theory and lived reality.

“The system is generous on paper – but the categories do not match lived reality.”
~ Regional service coordinator

Invisible Vulnerability

The absence of a distinct administrative status means that CBoCRSV:

- Cannot be counted as a population group in national statistics
- Are not included in service planning or resource forecasting
- Cannot be systematically followed through care systems or across regions
- Are unlikely to be identified in data informing policy, budgets, or international reporting obligations

When a group is not counted, it is not planned for—a risk compounded by the sensitive nature of conception circumstances and survivor reluctance to engage with the state.

Barriers in Accessing Benefits and Support

Frontline staff reported several systemic issues affecting access:

- Lack of standardised caseworker guidance leads to inconsistent classification.
- Families may avoid registering for benefits to prevent public exposure or administrative questioning.
- In some regions, social protection staff lack training in handling CRSV-linked cases confidentially or sensitively.
- Support programmes designed for other groups (e.g., orphans, displaced children) may not include services essential for CBoCRSV, such as attachment-focused mental health care, identity support, or long-term trauma-informed parenting interventions.

The result is a system where access to support is determined not by entitlement, but by narrative disclosure, geography, and professional interpretation.

Absence of Monitoring and Data Systems

Without a dedicated status, no systematic mechanism exists to:

- Track the number of CBoCRSV across regions
- Assess whether they are accessing available services
- Monitor long-term wellbeing outcomes
- Evaluate institutional response effectiveness

Workshop contributors stressed the sensitivity of tracking, noting that monitoring must protect anonymity, dignity, and security, while still enabling the State to fulfil obligations.

The solution is not population-level registries, but secure case-based information linked to rights—not identity labels. A clearly defined administrative identity does not mean public labelling or disclosure. Rather, it ensures that:

- Rights are **portable across institutions and regions**
- Eligibility for reparations, specialised services, and psychosocial support is **automatic—not conditional on storytelling**

- Adoption, alternative care, or displacement **do not erase entitlements**
- Long-term **protective and development needs** are recognised

This approach aligns with international jurisprudence that recognises children born of conflict-related rape as secondary victims of war crimes.

f. Reparations and Transitional Justice Measures

Ukraine has taken important steps toward establishing a national reparations framework for CRSV, including **the introduction of urgent interim reparations** for survivors and continued alignment with international standards on victim rights and transitional justice. These developments reflect a shift toward a survivor-centred approach that acknowledges harm and seeks to restore dignity, autonomy, and long-term wellbeing.

Reparations for CRSV in Ukraine currently focus primarily on the survivor (usually the mother), with measures including:

- One-time compensation under emerging reparations legislation
- Access to psychosocial, legal, and medical services
- Recognition within national victim status frameworks
- Integration into broader War Crimes documentation and accountability infrastructure

However, CBoCRSV are not yet explicitly recognised within reparations legislation or administrative procedures. Their position remains indirectly dependent on the legal status of the mother rather than on independent recognition as secondary victims of wartime violations.

Current Gaps and Barriers

Despite progress, several gaps limit equitable implementation:

- **No explicit legal entitlement for CBoCRSV:** Reparations frameworks do not yet formally recognise the child as a direct rights-holder harmed by the crime.
- **Administrative uncertainty:** Officials responsible for processing benefits reported limited clarity on eligibility rules and supporting documentation requirements, particularly for cases involving anonymous reporting or confidential adoption.
- **Procedural inconsistency:** Regional variability in application, verification, and approval processes results in inconsistent access.
- **Limited survivor-friendly pathways:** Concerns about stigma and fear of exposure continue to deter families from applying, even when eligible.
- **Absence of monitoring and oversight:** Without national-level tracking, it is unclear how many survivors or children access reparations, how long the process takes, or where implementation bottlenecks occur.

Participants noted that the system is new, evolving, and in pilot mode, requiring continued refinement and capacity-building.

Children as Rights-Holders Under Transitional Justice Principles

International transitional justice guidance, including practices from Bosnia, Colombia, and Rwanda, recognises children born of wartime sexual violence as **secondary victims of an international crime**. This positioning acknowledges:

- The harm inherent in conception through violence
- The lifelong consequences of stigma, identity loss, and social exclusion
- The child's autonomous right to justice, recognition, and remedy

"The mother and the child survive the same violence in different ways. The system must see both."

~ Child protection practitioner

Recognising CBoCRSV as rights-holders, rather than extensions of their mothers' victim status, reflects international standards on non-discrimination, child rights, and reparative justice.

Long-Term Reparations Needs

Reparations for CBoCRSV must consider lifespan needs, including:

- Identity-affirming support during childhood and adolescence
- Protection from stigma in public systems (education, healthcare, documentation)
- Access to medical records and genetic history where adoption or confidentiality applies
- Mental health support related to identity formation and trauma inheritance
- Potential future integration into truth-telling or memorialisation processes

Short-term cash benefits alone will not meet these needs. The Toolkit highlights models that combine financial, symbolic, and service-based reparations, creating holistic pathways for healing and reintegration.

Priorities for Future Reform

The assessment has identified the following requirements for future reform:

- Explicit legal recognition of CBoCRSV as a distinct category entitled to reparations
- Clear eligibility criteria and guidance for administrative bodies
- Survivor-safe application pathways that do not require disclosure to multiple institutions
- Integration of reparations into broader social services and identity systems
- Monitoring and evaluation mechanisms to ensure equity, accountability, and transparency

Crucially, legal reform must define CBoCRSV not as dependents of a recognised victim but as:

- **Direct beneficiaries of reparations**, with independent eligibility
- **Rights-holders** entitled to long-term protection, support, and recognition

g. Policy and Strategy Frameworks

Relevant strategies include:

- The National Action Plan on Women, Peace and Security (WPS)
- National child protection reform strategies
- Coordinated frameworks for survivor support and justice
- Disability and social inclusion roadmaps

Workshop participants emphasised that upcoming policy cycles must explicitly incorporate CBoCRSV – **not as a footnote, but as a dedicated category** with measurable indicators, defined institutional roles, and budgeted implementation measures.

h. Summary

Ukraine’s legal framework contains strong foundations and reflects meaningful progress. **However, fragmentation, inconsistent implementation, and gaps in identity, adoption, reparations, and social protection systems continue to affect children born of CRSV.**

Clear, harmonised legal status and coordinated policy execution remain essential next steps to ensure these children receive equal protection, dignified recognition, and long-term support.

V. KEY CHALLENGES IDENTIFIED

This section synthesises structural, legal, psychosocial, and social challenges affecting children born of conflict-related sexual violence and their mothers. The findings draw from legal review, stakeholder perspectives, and lived experience signals shared during workshops.

Challenges fall into five interconnected domains:

a. Stigma, Shame, and Social Perception

Stigma remains one of the most powerful barriers to accessing rights and services. It is shaped by historical gender norms, wartime narratives, and community attitudes.

Children born of CRSV risk being perceived as:

- “children of the enemy”
- “evidence” of sexual violence
- “unwanted” or “shameful history”

This framing impacts the mother as much as the child.

Stigma contributes to:

- Avoiding health and support services
- Withholding disclosure (sometimes even from close family)
- Pressured adoption or family separation

- Concealed identity history
- Interrupted attachment between mother and infant

The long-term impacts of stigma require public messaging strategies, workforce sensitisation, and survivor-led norm change.

*"It is not silence – it is shame.
Shame builds the walls."
~ Support worker*

b. Barriers to Accessing Services and Support

Even when legal pathways exist, survivors often face practical or emotional barriers to accessing help.

Common access barriers include:

- Fear of exposure in small communities
- Lack of confidentiality in local institutions
- Distrust of authorities after trauma
- Limited awareness of rights and available services
- Administrative complexity and inconsistent protocols

*"Help exists – but people are afraid of being seen asking for it."
~ Caseworker working with displaced families*

Mothers frequently make decisions based not on what is safest or healthiest—but what draws the least attention.

This signals the need for:

- Confidential pathways
- Survivor-informed communication strategies
- Clear national service standards

c. Lack of Harmonised Legal Status and Processes

Despite progress, the legal status of children born of CRSV remains fragmented across:

- Child protection frameworks
- Reparations criteria
- Adoption and identity laws
- Birth registration systems
- Social welfare eligibility categories

Without a clear and unified legal designation, rights vary depending on:

- Administrative region
- Caseworker interpretation

- Documentation availability
- The level of survivor advocacy

A child's access to identity, justice, and reparations should not depend on bureaucratic discretion.

d. Gaps in Trauma-Informed and Child-Centred Practice

Service systems are evolving, but capacity gaps remain in:

- Trauma-informed interviewing
- Safe identity support for children
- Supporting mother-child relationships after CRSV
- Intergenerational trauma prevention

“People working in the system care – but they do not always know how to respond without causing harm.”

~ Social worker

Several participants emphasised that many professionals want to help—but lack training, tools, or confidence.

This demonstrates the need for standardised training, cross-sector protocols, and supervision structures.

e. Limited National Monitoring and Data Systems

There is no coordinated mechanism to:

- Identify children born of CRSV
- Track services accessed
- Monitor wellbeing outcomes
- Assess identity and justice pathways

Without monitoring:

- Needs cannot be accurately forecasted
- Implementation progress remains unclear
- Policy cannot adapt based on evidence

Stakeholders noted the importance of developing ethical, secure, rights-based monitoring systems that avoid labelling or exposing children.

VI. SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION GAPS

While the legal and policy framework continues to strengthen, implementation remains uneven due to structural, operational, and capacity-related barriers.

a. Variation Across Regions

Decentralised service provision means that the experience of survivors and children varies widely depending on:

- Local leadership
- Resources and infrastructure
- Training availability
- Community attitudes

This results in “regional inequality of rights.”

b. Inconsistent Administrative Decision-Making

Survivors report different outcomes when applying for:

- Birth certificates
- Reparations
- Social benefits
- Adoption or guardianship pathways

Variability stems from:

- Unclear procedures
- Lack of harmonised training
- Ambiguous legal terminology

Clear national guidance is needed to ensure predictable and equitable implementation.

c. Fragmented Referral Pathways

There is currently no single coordinated entry point for support. Survivors may move between:

- Police
- Social services
- Medical institutions
- NGOs
- Courts
- Local government authorities

This increases emotional burden and risk of secondary trauma.

d. Workforce Support and Burnout Risks

Professionals supporting survivors described emotional exhaustion and limited guidance.

Ongoing training, supervision, and mental health support for service providers are essential.

“We are trying to do the right thing – but sometimes we feel we are building the system while already running it.”

~ Child protection official

e. Limited Public Communication Strategy

There is no unified national messaging effort addressing:

- Myths
- Discrimination
- Rights
- Protective narratives

Yet stakeholders widely recognised that if Ukraine does this, it would be the first country in active war to build a positive narrative for these children. This creates both urgency and opportunity.

VII. PRIORITY ACTION AREAS

This section proposes actionable policy directions based on the legal analysis and workshop findings. The actions address legal clarity, coordinated implementation, stigma reduction, identity protection, and long-term psychosocial support. Each area includes strategic objectives, operational considerations, and risks if unaddressed.

a. Establish a Clear Legal Status for Children Born of CRSV

Ensure CBoCRSV are recognised across legal, health, justice, and social protection systems through a harmonised definition and status category.

Operational Actions

- Amend relevant national legislation to define CBoCRSV consistently.
- Align and consolidate eligibility criteria for rights, benefits, and reparations.
- Ensure the legal category protects anonymity while enabling entitlement tracking.
- Review adoption and registry law to safeguard the child's right to future identity information.

Why It Matters

A unified legal category prevents fragmented support and ensures consistency across regions and administrative systems.

Risks if Not Implemented

- Unequal access to benefits and services
- Permanent loss of identity, rights, or reparations
- Reinforcement of stigma through bureaucratic ambiguity

"A child's access to rights should not depend on which office door they walk through."

~ Legal practitioner

b. Strengthen Confidential, Survivor-Centred Access to Services

Ensure mothers and children can access services safely, without discrimination or fear of exposure.

Operational Actions

- Establish confidential referral pathways with trained personnel.
- Integrate trauma-informed procedures into maternity care, birth registration, and psychosocial support.
- Expand alternatives to in-person disclosure where appropriate (hotlines, encrypted digital intake forms).
- Provide specialised services for mothers struggling with parenting after CRSV.

Why It Matters

Fear of being identified remains a powerful deterrent, especially in small communities.

*"Help exists, but people are afraid to be seen asking for it."
~ Psychologist*

Risks if Not Implemented

- Delayed or avoided registration and healthcare
- Increased mental health burden and attachment difficulties
- Increased likelihood of unlawful or pressured adoption

c. Create a Coordinated Multi-Sector Service System

Ensure predictable, connected support from first contact through long-term care using clear national standards.

Operational Actions

- Develop a national referral and case management framework.
- Assign defined responsibilities across justice, health, education, and social services.
- Establish a national helpline mechanism and a single entry system in coordination with NGOs.
- Create monitoring and accountability mechanisms for compliance with implementation standards.

Why It Matters

Survivors currently navigate a complex and fragmented system.

"There is no one door – only many corridors."

– *Service provider*

Risks if Not Implemented

- Continued fragmentation
- Secondary trauma from repeated retelling
- Administrative inequity and service gaps

d. Develop a National Public Awareness and Stigma Reduction Strategy

Foster an environment where CBoCRSV and their families can live without discrimination or social exclusion.

Operational Actions

- Launch a national campaign focused on dignity, belonging, and human rights.
- Use survivor-approved messaging informed by research on public attitudes.
- Include rural communities, educators, clergy, and social service networks.
- Integrate messaging into school curricula, public health materials, and national media.

Why It Matters

Public perception directly influences whether families seek help and whether children are treated with dignity.

“The narrative determines whether the child is welcomed – or whispered about.”

~ Survivor advocate

Risks if Not Implemented

- Normalisation of stigma
- Increased isolation and intergenerational harm
- Lack of societal readiness for legal reforms

e. Build Workforce Capacity and Professional Support Systems

Equip frontline workers with training, tools, and ongoing supervision to safely support families affected by CRSV.

Operational Actions

- Create standardised national training modules (health, justice, social services, education).
- Provide vicarious trauma support and mentoring for professionals.
- Certify specialists in child trauma and CRSV-related care.
- Ensure training includes cultural and conflict-sensitivity modules.

Why It Matters

Frontline responses shape survivor trust, service uptake, and long-term healing.

“People want to help – but are afraid to say or do the wrong thing.”

~ Social worker

Risks if Not Implemented

- Harmful or retraumatising interactions
- Inconsistent protection practices across regions
- Workforce burnout and turnover

f. Establish Ethical, Secure Monitoring and Data Systems

Create mechanisms to track implementation, identify gaps, and plan services – without labelling, exposing, or harming children.

Operational Actions

- Develop an ethical data governance model with anonymised tracking.
- Ensure compliance with data protection and child rights frameworks.
- Introduce routine monitoring indicators for ministries and partners.
- Produce annual reports to guide resource allocation and policy evaluation.

Why It Matters

Systems cannot improve what they do not accurately measure. We cannot protect what we cannot see – but we must never expose these children.

Risks if Not Implemented

- Policy misalignment
- Service gaps and duplication
- Loss of accountability

VIII. IMPLEMENTATION ROADMAP

Ukraine is building the legal and service infrastructure necessary to recognise and support CBoCRSV. The next phase requires coordinated and phased implementation across justice, social protection, health, and policy systems to ensure that rights move from legal provision to lived reality.

The implementation roadmap below outlines actionable steps across short-, medium-, and long-term timeframes, grounded in feasibility, system readiness, and alignment with national reform processes. It assumes a survivor- and child-centred approach, prioritising confidentiality, dignity, and protection from harm.

“We do not need everything perfect on day one – we need steady steps that build trust and protection.”

This framework is designed to evolve over time. Early actions focus on clarity, safety, and procedural alignment. Medium-term actions aim to consolidate system coherence. Long-term planning focuses on sustainability, monitoring, and ensuring that identity and support rights follow the child throughout their development.

a. Implementation Framework Table

Priority Area	Key Implementation Actions	Lead Actors	Timeline	Enabling Conditions / Dependencies
1. Legal Recognition & Status Harmonisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establish a harmonised legal definition of CBoCRSV across criminal, civil, social protection, and reparations law. 			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Amend or align legislation on documentation, identity rights, reparations eligibility, and adoption/sealed records. 	Parliament, Ministry of Justice, MoSP, Child Ombudsperson Office	Short-Medium Term (6-18 months)	Requires legal drafting coordination and alignment with WPS Action Plan and emerging reparations law.	
2. Confidential Access to Services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop national protocols ensuring confidential, non-stigmatising access to birth registration, health care, psychosocial support, and legal assistance. 			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Create alternative pathways for survivors uncomfortable with in-person disclosure. 	Ministry of Health, MoSP, civil registry authorities, NGOs	Immediate-Short Term (3-12 months)	Requires national guidance, training roll-out, and digital options for secure disclosure.	
3. Coordinated Referral and Case	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establish a coordinated national referral mechanism with defined entry points. 			

Management Pathways				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integrate CBoCRSV into existing GBV/CRSV and child protection referral maps. 				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pilot specialised case management models in conflict-affected regions. 	MoSP, Prosecutor General's Office, National Social Service, local authorities	Medium Term (12-24 months)	Must align with local governance structures and existing reform processes.	
4. Public Information and Stigma Reduction Strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop messaging grounded in research and survivor consultation. 			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Launch phased national communications addressing stigma, rights, and equality. 				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Embed content in schools, health system materials, and media partnerships. 	Government Communications Service, Ministry of Culture, Ministry of Education, CSOs	Medium-Long Term (6-36 months)	Requires coordinated messaging governance and evidence-based testing to avoid unintended harm.	
5. Workforce Strengthening &	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop national training modules on trauma-informed practice, 			

Professional Standards	confidentiality, CRSV law, and child rights.			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutionalise training in pre-service education for legal, health, social, and education professions. 				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create supervision and burnout-prevention mechanisms. 	National Service Training Academies, MoH, MoJ, universities	Immediate-Long Term (6-36 months)	Needs dedicated budget line and integration into accreditation pathways.	
6. Ethical Monitoring & Data Systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design a confidential monitoring system to track implementation without labelling or exposing children. 			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish indicators for equity, uptake, timeliness, and rights fulfilment. 				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publish anonymised annual progress reporting. 	National Statistics Bureau, MoSP, Ombudsperson Office, academic partners	Medium-Long Term (12-36 months)	Must meet high standards on data protection, safeguarding, and purpose limitation.	

IX. Conclusion

Ukraine stands at a pivotal moment. The systems, legislative reforms, and public conversations emerging around conflict-related sexual violence demonstrate a clear commitment to justice and dignity. Yet the children born of that violence – and the mothers who survived it – represent a group whose rights, identity, and wellbeing must be safeguarded not only through law, but through long-term societal recognition and care.

The work reflected in this report shows that progress is already underway: legal amendments, improved documentation pathways, specialised investigative structures, and a growing professional community committed to survivor-centred practice. These developments form a strong foundation.

“We cannot change what happened – but we can decide what kind of future these children grow into.”

However, the next steps require intention. A holistic and coordinated approach – grounded in trauma-informed systems, the best interests of the child, and survivor participation – is essential to ensure that children born of CRSV are not defined by harm, but by the protections and opportunities guaranteed to them as equal rights-holders under Ukrainian law and international standards.

If implemented fully, this framework has the potential to become a global model. Few nations have attempted to address the rights of children born of war in real time. Ukraine can lead not only in legislating recognition – but in demonstrating what it means to build a society where every child is valued, protected, and invited to belong.

Ensuring that future is safe, dignified, and supported is both a legal obligation and a moral choice – one that aligns with Ukraine’s broader vision of justice, resilience, and recovery.

Annex: Ukrainian Laws and Policy Documents Reviewed

This annex lists the principal legal, policy, and institutional frameworks reviewed as part of the assessment of protections for children born of conflict-related sexual violence (CBoCRSV) in Ukraine. The review considered legislation, policies, procedural frameworks, and international commitments relevant to child rights, conflict-related sexual violence (CRSV), legal identity, reparations, social protection, justice, non-discrimination, education, health, and participation.

a. Constitutional and Foundational Frameworks

- Constitution of Ukraine No. 254k/96-VR of 28 June 1996
- Law of Ukraine on the Principles of Preventing and Combating Discrimination in Ukraine No. 5207-VI of 6 September 2012

b. Child Protection and Child Rights

- Law of Ukraine “On the Protection of Childhood” No. 2402-III of 26 April 2001
- Law of Ukraine “On Bodies and Services on Children Affairs and Special Establishments for Children” No. 20/95-VR of 24 January 1995
- Law of Ukraine “On Ensuring Organisational-Legal Conditions for Social Protection of Orphans and Children Deprived of Parental Care” No. 2342-IV of 13 January 2005
- Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine No. 585 “On Ensuring Social Protection of Children in Difficult Life Circumstances” of 1 June 2020
- Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine No. 268 “Procedure for Granting the Status of a Child Affected by Hostilities and Armed Conflicts” of 5 April 2017

c. Conflict-Related Sexual Violence and War-Affected Children

- Law of Ukraine “On Social Protection and Support of Children Affected by the Armed Aggression of the Russian Federation against Ukraine, and Amendments to Certain Legislative Acts of Ukraine on Streamlining the Provision of Social Services and Payments” No. 3999-IX of 8 October 2024
- Law of Ukraine “On Legal and Social Protection of Survivors of Sexual Violence Related to the Armed Aggression of the Russian Federation against Ukraine and Providing Them with Urgent Interim Reparations” No. 4067-IX of 20 November 2024
- National Action Plan on Women, Peace and Security until 2025 No. 1544-r of 28 October 2020

d. Family Law, Civil Status and Identity

- Family Code of Ukraine No. 2947-III of 10 January 2002
- Civil Code of Ukraine No. 435-IV of 15 January 2003
- Civil Procedure Code of Ukraine No. 1618-IV of 18 March 2004

- Law of Ukraine “On State Registration of Civil Status Acts” No. 2398-VI of 1 July 2010
- Law of Ukraine “On Citizenship of Ukraine” No. 2235-III of 18 January 2001
- Law of Ukraine “On Amendments to Some Legislative Acts of Ukraine on Strengthening Social Protection of Children and Supporting Families with Children” No. 936-VIII of 26 January 2016
- Draft Law No. 7087 “On Amendments to Certain Legislative Acts of Ukraine Regarding the Delineation of Functions of State Authorities and Local Self-Government Authorities on the Protection of Children’s Rights” (22 February 2022)
- Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine No. 9 “Procedure for Confirming the Fact of Birth of a Child Outside a Health Care Institution” of 9 January 2013

e. Criminal Justice and Accountability

- Criminal Code of Ukraine No. 2341-III of 5 April 2001
- Criminal Procedure Code of Ukraine No. 4651-VI of 13 April 2012

f. Education

- Law of Ukraine “On Education” No. 2145-VIII of 5 September 2017

g. Health and Mental Health

- Law of Ukraine “On the Foundations of Ukraine’s Healthcare System” No. 2801-XII of 19 November 1992
- Law of Ukraine “On the Mental Health Care System” No. 4223-IX of 15 January 2025

h. Social Protection

- Draft Law “On the Foundations of Social Protection of Children Affected by the Full-Scale Armed Aggression of the Russian Federation against Ukraine”